

D5.1: Article on mapping of challenges and presentation of ethical, legal, regulatory, and technical interoperability solutions

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ABSTRACT:	<p>This report, produced as part of the XR4Human project, provides a comprehensive mapping of the ethical, legal, regulatory, and technical challenges associated with XR technologies. Drawing insights from various project work packages, it identifies thematic overlaps across ethics, policy, and interoperability reviews. Key findings include risks related to privacy, data protection, psychological and physical health, discrimination, accessibility, and market barriers. Furthermore, the report proposes solutions such as a European Code of Conduct, Interoperability Guidelines, and educational tools to foster an equitable, inclusive, and sustainable XR ecosystem. By engaging with diverse stakeholders—including policymakers, industry bodies, researchers, and end-users—the report emphasises a human-centred approach to XR technologies adoption, advocating for the integration of ethical principles, inclusivity, and technical standards to address emerging challenges effectively.</p>
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Keyword List:	Extended Reality, Virtual Reality, Augmented Reality, Mixed Reality, data protection, ethics, interoperability, inclusivity, accessibility, human-centred design.
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1. Background

The pace of technological developments provides capabilities that affect almost every aspect of our lives. We live in a time of great consequence where the decisions we are making today will have an exponential effect on our tomorrow. Over the last few decades, we are increasingly witnessing the phenomenon of technological convergence, i.e., the amalgamation of previously unrelated technologies. Around the turn of the millennium, we often used the term technological convergence to describe the phenomenon of the early smartphones which, in addition to phone calls, offered the functionalities of cameras, calendars, basic internet access, and even simple games. Over the last twenty years, we have seen further progress in terms of technological convergence. Today's technological innovations offer convergence not just for different technical capabilities converging on a device (and between devices and networks), but where the digital world converges with the physical world. The initial rudimentary glimpses of a future world created by the fusion of bits and atoms are just starting to appear. For decades futurists and sci-fi authors have envisioned the world with both utopian and dystopian flavours, but this has been, until this point in time, beyond the limits of technology. Those limits are being constantly transcended, driven by massive performance gains in processing power, big data, sensors, cloud computing, low latency high speed networking and machine learning algorithms. The phenomenon of bringing together, interweaving, or offering the chance to navigate between the physical world and virtual environments comprises the domain of extended reality (XR), which includes virtual reality (VR), augmented reality (AR), mixed reality (MR) and the spectrum therein.

XR technologies have rapidly evolved in the past decade. These technologies offer a major change in terms of the immersive and experiential quality of availing digital services, and therefore have a unique potential to be used in a wide array of purposes, including media and entertainment, upskilling and training, urban planning, and education (amongst others). However, the rising adoption of XR across various fields exposes individuals to both existing risks of technology, as well as subjecting them to new potential harms through the unique features of XR technologies.

Considering these factors, the XR4Human project aims to identify an ethical and human-centred development process for XR technologies. This includes engaging with European XR stakeholders, analysing the ethical, regulatory and governance issues arising from XR technologies, and creating a European Code of Conduct for Equitable, Inclusive and Human-centred XR Technologies. Stakeholder feedback was particularly important in addressing specific issues raised by the work packages, such as concerns around privacy and data protection, discrimination and physical health risks. Additionally, the project will deliver Interoperability Guidelines, an experience library featuring test cases for demonstration and validation, a rating system, and an educational toolbox.

Throughout the project, XR4Human will provide a comprehensive rating system and supplemental educational materials for end-users and for the public. These resources aim to increase awareness and help individuals and the society at large to adapt to responsible XR technologies. The Code of Conduct and the Interoperability Guidelines will be integrated with the rating system. The XR4Human project comprises several deliverables, each focusing on a particular perspective through which XR technologies are analysed. The project takes a multidisciplinary and multistakeholder approach.

Accordingly, the assessments, frameworks and guidance documents created through the WPs shall rely on the reflective equilibrium process. Through the reflective equilibrium process, the XR4Human project team continuously engages in a reflective process that considers factually informed judgments, principles, rules, theoretical considerations, and moral intuitions and keeps revising these elements wherever necessary in order to achieve an acceptable coherence amongst them.¹ Stakeholder feedback was integral to this process, as it completed the findings of WPs 2, 3 and 4 by providing real-world insights in the challenges such as barriers to accessibility, the risks of emotional manipulation and the need for improved safety features,

This report is written as part of WP 5, which aims to identify, map and examine the relevant stakeholders, issues, emerging requirements and solutions highlighted in previous work packages. D5.1 incorporated stakeholder feedback directly into its analysis of impacts and roles. Stakeholders provided critical input including highlighting the challenges faced by bystanders, the need for improved safety metrics and measures, and the educational value of XR technologies. This feedback has informed by the mapping of stakeholder roles and the practical recommendations outlined in this report. How the stakeholder input complements the work of the WPs is noted below.

To identify human-centred development processes, WP 1 aims to ensure an inclusive, comprehensive, and holistic approach to stakeholder engagement. This involves monitoring and identifying stakeholder groups, establishing channels of communication with such groups, creating value for each stakeholder group, involving them in the project's activities, ensuring collaboration towards multi-stakeholder participation, empowering stakeholder groups to achieve democratic and inclusive engagement, and innovating by creating new goals and developing cooperation. The XR4Human project identifies the four broad domains of stakeholders involved in resolving issues with XR technologies, i.e., society/governance, industry, research and academic organisations, and individuals.^{2,3} These stakeholders are key to reporting, formulating, implementing, and supervising the solutions to address the challenges raised by XR technologies. Additionally, WP 1 aims to foster and increase engagement between the XR4Human project and the stakeholder community by creating a Forum to ensure interaction and collaboration between the stakeholders.⁴ Stakeholder feedback was integral to validating the approach outlined in WP1. For D5.1 the forum-based responses and structured interviews highlighted the importance of these clear communication channels for engagement. These help ensure the inclusivity for economically disadvantaged groups and for the incorporation of adaptive and human-centred design practices that enhance accessibility. The received input also shaped recommendations for fostering stronger collaborations between stakeholders ensuring that this engagement aligned with democratic and human-centred principles.

¹XR4Human Project Proposal document, 'The Equitable, Inclusive, and Human-Centered XR Project (XR4HUMAN)' HORIZON-CL4-2021-HUMAN-01-28, p. 6.-12.

²D1.1, p. 23.

³An extended set of stakeholders have been identified in the XR4Human Project Proposal document, which includes (a) associations of industries and developers, (b) research policy makers, (c) legal experts, (d) researchers and programmers, (e) members of RECs, (f) science journalists, (g) users of XR technologies, and (h) lay people with no knowledge or experience in using XR technologies. Please see XR4Human, 'The Equitable, Inclusive, and Human-Centered XR Project (XR4HUMAN)' HORIZON-CL4-2021-HUMAN-01-28, p. 12.

⁴D1.1, p. 34.

WP 2, in turn, aims to review and engage with the ethical issues presented by XR technologies. The first step in this analysis involves identifying the relevant ethical frameworks, codes of conduct and good practices relevant for XR technologies. Through an extensive literature review, WP 2 has identified three primary thematic categories where XR technologies present ethical issues, namely, (a) data and the use of technology, (b) human rights, and (c) societal, economic, and environmental concerns. Similarly, WP 2 has identified six foundational values and twenty-two principles that are cited in a recurring manner as relevant for XR technologies. In an iterative process, WP 2 connects the ethical principles relevant to foundational values and has identified the key foundational values and ethical principles at play in detail. The dominant principles being discussed are the principles of privacy, informed consent, responsibility, transparency, and freedom. Similarly, the foundational values at play have been identified as respect for persons, well-being, safety, integrity and trust, justice, and responsiveness. These domains clearly overlap with the four personas of relevant stakeholders highlighted above. WP 2 notes the role played by stakeholders in each domain. For example, ethical issues relating to data, technology and human rights require the enforcement of existing laws, and to expand the scope of existing laws to recognise new forms of harms afforded by XR technologies, which require the involvement of policymakers.⁵ Similarly, the role of industry has been identified as key for ensuring inclusive and human-centred design, as well as by adopting ethical values into codes of conduct or self-regulatory guidelines.⁶ Research and academic organisations play a key role in reviewing and disseminating awareness regarding the effects of XR technologies for broadening the existing ethical discourse and helping develop new ethics and codes for further research.⁷ Finally, the general public, including both users and non-users of XR technologies, must be appropriately sensitised and made aware as to both their benefits and risks, and the extent to which their own rights can be exercised through law.⁸

Another extensive scoping review performed by WP2 (D2.2) identifies potential risks and harms associated with XR technologies, categorising them into six main themes: health and wellbeing, autonomy, epistemic and scientific, normative, structural, and technical safety and security. These themes cover a wide range of issues, from cognitive and physical health impacts to privacy concerns and legal challenges, emphasising the need for comprehensive risk mapping and responsible development practices. Additionally, WP2 compared these findings with the perceptions of European citizens, as gathered by the 2023 European Citizens' Panel on Virtual Worlds. The citizens' concerns largely align with the scoping review, highlighting mental health, data privacy, ethical standards, economic impacts, and the need for secure digital environments, while also emphasising environmental sustainability.⁹ Stakeholder feedback reinforced the risks identified in D2.2, particularly in the categories of health and wellbeing, autonomy and structural safety. For example, participants provided examples of simulator sickness in real-world cases, underscoring the urgency of implementing safety protocols and additional research on the matter. Additionally, feedback from accessibility advocates emphasised the structural barriers faced by differently abled individuals, leading to stronger recommendations for universal design principles.

The issues emanating from the ethical review of XR technologies have significant overlaps with the policy issues identified in the reports of WP 3. The first report of WP 3, D3.1, identifies the opportunities and potential

⁵D2.1, p. 24.

⁶D2.1, p. 24.

⁷D2.1, p. 25.

⁸D2.1, p. 25.

⁹D2.2.

of XR technologies, and notes its adoption in seven key sectors, i.e., media and entertainment, work and production processes, medical processes and healthcare, marketing and trade, security, education, and in urban planning and conservation. D3.1 highlights the use-case scenarios for XR technologies in each of these sectors and cites numerous policy issues presented by their application in their use. In addition to these sector-specific risks, D3.1 also highlights broader social and regulatory challenges presented by XR technologies by analysing its implications for child safety, psychological impacts, effects on relationships and effects on democratic processes. Stakeholder feedback complemented WP3's sectoral analysis by raising specific concerns about child safety in educational XR experiences and emotional manipulation in marketing and trade. Feedback also underscored the need for policy measures to address power imbalances between employers and employees in XR-based training and workplace environments, aligning with D3.1 focus on safeguarding agency and autonomy. The second report, D3.2, identified the extent to which the existing regulatory landscape applies to XR technologies, which is necessary to identify gaps or instances of over-regulation across areas including privacy and data protection, intellectual property, consumer and competition law, media and online services, cybersecurity, accessibility and non-discrimination, sectoral and technology law, and finance law.¹⁰

Lastly, WP 4 aims to identify and analyse the existing state of XR technologies from the lens of interoperability. This is an important aspect of the XR4Human project as ensuring greater interoperability is key to making XR technologies human-centred in nature, accessible and lowers the bar of adoption. In its initial report, WP4 identifies key gaps and limitations in interoperability, including (a) the lack of interoperability between the two-dimensional experience of a user's existing digital life and the three-dimensional spaces that form the core of XR technologies, (b) the user's inability to change existing two-dimensional layouts of digital interactions into three-dimensional layouts, hindering their ability to conceptualise three-dimensional spaces, and (c) the development of XR technologies not being based on standardisation. XR technologies has a potential to enable differently abled persons to meaningfully participate in society.¹¹ Similarly, the COVID-19 pandemic, and the subsequent rise in online therapy, shows that technologically-driven solutions such as therapy through XR technologies can lower barriers of access for elderly people, differently abled people or people living far from specialised care.¹² In addition, WP 4 notes the development of XR-related standards both by private non-profit entities as well as inter-governmental standardisation bodies. It highlights the goals of the Interoperability Guidance Document, which involve ensuring technical interoperability, human-centred interoperability, and policy and legal interoperability. Importantly, WP 4 highlights the need for ethical and policy concerns to be aligned with interoperability throughout the process of building interoperable systems, as opposed to being provided as an afterthought. Stakeholders also emphasised the importance of aligning interoperability standards with accessibility goals. Specific feedback included the calls for adaptive interfaces to accommodate users of all abilities and ensuring that XR systems integrate with assistive technologies, another layer of interoperability.

¹⁰D3.2.

¹¹Radanliev, P., et al. (2024). Accessibility and inclusiveness of new information and communication technologies for disabled users and content creators in the metaverse. *Disability and Rehabilitation: Assistive Technology*, 19(5). <https://doi.org/10.1080/17483107.2023.2241882>.

¹²Pons, P., et al. (2022). Extended reality for mental health: Current trends and future challenges. *Frontiers in Computer Science*, 4. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fcomp.2022.1034307>.

2. Objective of this report

This report aims to map and identify thematic similarities within the issues flagged by the review of the ethical, policy, regulatory and interoperability aspects of XR technologies conducted by WPs 2, 3, and 4. Further, this report aims to identify and highlight the solutions to these issues as discussed in these work packages. Lastly, it also aims to map these issues and solutions with the relevant stakeholder groups identified by the XR4Human Proposal.¹³

The input from WPs 2, 3 and 4 provided the foundation for stakeholder engagement activities conducted as this part of the report. Stakeholder feedback was collected through a two-pronged approach involving written input via structured survey based on forum prompts and semi-structured interviews with relevant stakeholders. These engagements allowed stakeholders to respond to the challenges raised in the work packages enriching the analysis with practical insights.

The feedback gathered from stakeholders informed additions made both to the impacts of XR technologies and the roles of the stakeholders as described in each section of the report. This integration ensured that the findings are grounded in a comprehensive multi-stakeholder perspective and align with the goals of the XR4Human Proposal.

¹³ Including representatives from industry, policymakers, legal experts, and researchers.

3. Identifying common challenges & Role of Stakeholders

As discussed above, the XR4Human project has reviewed the impact of XR technologies through the lens of ethics, policy, and interoperability. This multi-disciplinary approach reveals overlaps in the issues with XR technologies and helps to identify key concerns that need to be addressed by the Code of Conduct. This report aims to map these reviews by identifying commonalities in these concerns. Further, this report will identify challenges faced by key stakeholders as well as the role of stakeholders in addressing them. In doing so, the stakeholders are identified within the domains of stakeholders discussed in WP 1, i.e., society/governance, industry, research and academic organisations, and individuals. These domains must also reflect the perspectives of underrepresented groups, such as economically disadvantaged individuals and individuals with disabilities, whose experiences are critical to addressing disparities and fostering inclusivity in XR adoption. It must be noted at this juncture that classifications within stakeholders are not mutually exclusive and merely serve to indicate the key stakeholders at play. Lastly, by listing the commonalities of impact due to XR technologies, this report identifies the role of specific stakeholders primarily as a means of enabling stakeholder consultation by focused discussions with the relevant key stakeholders mentioned below. This report acknowledges that in addition to the listed stakeholders, several other stakeholders, including users and developers themselves, play a broader role in addressing the impacts of XR technologies through their actions.

Figure 1: Comprehensive stakeholder list as referenced in the XR4Human project proposal¹⁴

3.1. Privacy and data protection issues

The most prominent thematic issue that arises from the ethical and policy review conducted by WPs 2 and 3 relates to the issue of privacy and data protection. XR technologies may involve capturing personal biometric data relating through both direct and indirect means. For example, VR operates by compiling ‘kinematic fingerprints’ by tracking the user’s motion via personal (biometric) datapoints, i.e., head, hand and eye movements, voice, facial expressions and gestures.¹⁵ Similarly, AR involves overlaying digitally created content including imagery over the user’s immediate physical surroundings while incorporating real-time

¹⁴An extended set of stakeholders have been identified in the XR4Human Project Proposal document listed in XR4Human, ‘The Equitable, Inclusive, and Human-Centered XR Project (XR4HUMAN)’ HORIZON-CL4-2021-HUMAN-01-28, p. 12.

¹⁵Rathenau Instituut (2020) cited in D3.1 in p. 11.

inputs to create an enhanced version of reality. This necessarily involves processing data relating to the user's surroundings and could potentially even process the personal biometric data of non-users in its vicinity. Lastly, MR creates hybrid, artificial experiences that seamlessly blend or merge a digital environment with the physical environment and computer-generated landscapes, involving various elements of VR and AR technologies, and their need for extensive personal data processing, in its operations.¹⁶ Further, MR technologies involve capturing data from the user's immediate surroundings, increasing the chances of non-consensual personal data processing from bystanders. This extensive processing of personal data through XR technologies presents another avenue for businesses to engage in datafication, transforming actions by users into quantified data and allowing the data controllers to monitor and profile their users.¹⁷ Researchers further note the negative effects of XR technologies being adopted in workplaces, to 'datafy' and evaluate workplace performance for service sector jobs such as retail.¹⁸

A study conducted by the University of California Berkeley notes that 55,541 VR users could be identified from their head and hand movement data, and the relative ability of these individuals being uniquely identifiable only based on their physiological characteristics.¹⁹ The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) defines biometric data as "personal data resulting from specific technical processing relating to the physical, physiological or behavioural characteristics of a natural person, which allow or confirm the unique identification of that natural person, such as facial images or dactyloscopic data".²⁰ Under the GDPR, biometric data is considered as part of the special categories of personal data, which merit higher standards of protection as their processing could create significant risks to fundamental rights and freedoms of individuals.²¹ For this reason, special categories of personal data, including biometric data, are generally prohibited from being processed except under specific grounds which include the user's explicit consent for specified purposes.²²

D2.1 highlights the issues with data privacy and data protection, noting that XR technologies presents multi-faceted risks in terms of data breaches, constant capture without consent, the possibility of the data being converted into identifiable data, and the lack of true informed consent due to data obfuscation.²³ D3.1 notes the need for greater data security in the use of XR technologies in manufacturing processes, at both the operating system and the applications running on the XR device, to prevent harms both to employee data as well as corporate secrets and confidential information.²⁴ This concern highlights the need for interoperability

¹⁶D3.1, p. 12.

¹⁷Bibri, S. E. (2023). The metaverse as a virtual model of platform urbanism: Its converging AIoT, XReality, neurotech, and nanobiotech and their applications, challenges, and risks. *Smart Cities*, 6(3), 1–22. <https://www.mdpi.com/2624-6511/6/3/65/pdf>.

¹⁸Egliston, B., & Carter, M. (2021). Critical questions for Facebook's virtual reality: Data, power and the metaverse. *Internet Policy Review*, 10(4), 1–20. <https://eprints.qut.edu.au/230384/1/109122886.pdf>.

¹⁹Nair et al (2023), cited in D3.1, p. 16.

²⁰European Union. (2016). *Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data (General Data Protection Regulation), Recital 51. Official Journal of the European Union, L119, 1–88.* Retrieved from <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32016R0679>.

²¹ibid.

²²ibid.

²³D2.1, p. 16.

²⁴ D3.1, p. 19.

in data security standards for all devices and software that comprise XR technologies. Concurrently, D3.1 identified issues pertaining to privacy and data protection in each of the seven sectors in its review.²⁵ The concerns with hacking and the risk of audio or video deepfakes, considering the kind of biometric personal data being processed in the media and entertainment applications sector, were also highlighted.²⁶

The adoption of XR technologies in the work and production sector raise unique concerns of whether consent could be considered freely given, and whether XR technologies could be used to process employee data for the purposes of evaluation (which could be considered profiling), or workplace surveillance by tracking employee movements.²⁷ In the medical and healthcare sector, the use of XR technologies for the purposes of training professionals or for treating patients would involve processing health data, another special category of personal data protected by the GDPR, which may cause patients to be uniquely identifiable.²⁸ In the marketing sector, the major risk to privacy and data protection stems from the massive amounts of data that can be processed by advertisers through XR technologies applications, risking emotional manipulation or intrusive levels of profiling of consumers.²⁹ In the security sector, there are grave data protection risks as XR technologies may risk classified information data breaches, as well as the rise in smart policing through XR technologies which may give rise to warrantless police surveillance.³⁰ The use of XR technologies in the workplace, and the associated training of employees, raises the risks of exposure of employee personal data and other confidential information to third parties.³¹ The risks in the use of XR in the education sector mirror the risks in the work and production sector, with questions on the validity of consent given by the students when XR technologies is used for teaching courses or individual evaluation.³² In this regard, the GDPR requires that for children under the age of 16 years, consent must be obtained from their parent or guardian.³³ Lastly, the use of XR technologies in urban planning involves capturing data in a world-facing manner, with simultaneous localisation and mapping potential. This application risks capturing personal data from bystanders who may not consent to their personal data being collected.³⁴

3.1.1. Impact on stakeholders

The above privacy and data protection issues, highlighted by D2.1 and D3.1, impact the following stakeholders:

- (a) **Individual users:** This topic deals with concerns directly impacting the users of XR technologies. XR technologies, as noted above, may involve significant processing of personal data and special categories of personal data. They present risks such as undermining the agency of users, failing to

²⁵D3.1 of the XR4Human project reviews seven key sectors where XR technologies are applied: Media and Entertainment, Work and Production Processes, Medical and Healthcare, Marketing and Trade, Security, Education, and Urban Planning and Conservation.

²⁶D3.1, p. 16.

²⁷D3.1, p. 18.

²⁸D3.1, p. 22.

²⁹D3.1, p. 23-24.

³⁰D3.1, p. 26.

³¹XR4Human Project Proposal document listed in XR4Human, 'The Equitable, Inclusive, and Human-Centered XR Project (XR4HUMAN) HORIZON-CL4-2021-HUMAN-01-28; see also D 3.1, p. 25.

³²D 3.1, p. 29-30.

³³Art. 8(1), GDPR.

³⁴D 3.1, p. 33-34.

adequately inform users regarding the scope and breadth of data processing, increased harm due to data breaches, and sharing of data with third parties without the consent of the user. Additionally, like social media services, XR services may encourage users to become content creators – thus generating and processing greater amounts of personal data. These issues require increased digital literacy and awareness of the technology and the data subject’s rights under various laws, which is a key facet to the XR4Human project. When XR technologies are adopted in workplaces or educational institutions, this deployment raises further questions on whether users are truly capable of giving consent given the power imbalances at play, requiring the controller to justify the processing under different legal grounds. Obliging employees or students to use XR technologies may create a chilling effect on them, as data regarding their actions is captured and can be reviewed by the institution, creating an atmosphere of surveillance. The use of XR technologies in marketing, and the attendant processing of personal data, poses risks of user profiling and manipulation through the user’s natural gaze behaviour to tracking by inferring their cognitive state.³⁵

- (b) **General public excluding users:** D3.1 highlights the impact of AR technologies on bystanders and the general public.³⁶ AR technologies require processing of data relating to the real-world environment around the user and may capture the personal data of individuals without obtaining their consent. The collection of such data, particularly biometric or location-based information, raises ethical concerns and challenges of compliance with the GDPR.³⁷ XR service providers are required to adhere to GDPR principles for processing personal data, including ensuring transparency and offering data subject rights to bystanders, including the rights to object to processing and to erasure. In shared public settings, these risks are heightened since XR use may normalise intrusive surveillance practices.³⁸ The lack of recourse or awareness among non-users regarding how their data is captured and processed, exacerbates these concerns. Stricter compliance measures, public awareness initiatives, and clear accountability mechanisms are critical to safeguarding privacy for all individuals, including non-users.

3.1.2. Role of stakeholders in addressing challenges

In its foundational values and principles, D2.1 highlighted the principles of informed consent, privacy and confidentiality and the right to withdraw as part of the larger value of ‘respect for persons.’ It further highlighted the principles of accountability and transparency as part of the larger normative values of integrity and trust.³⁹ These principles offer valuable guidance towards ensuring value-sensitive design of XR technologies to address these risks. Further, D3.1 pointed out that the GDPR is a key tool in combating the risks posed by XR technologies in the above sectors. However, these issues raise questions on whether the GDPR sufficiently

³⁵Sendilnathan, N., et al. (2024, May 11). Implicit gaze research for XR systems. *PhysioCHI: Towards Best Practices for Integrating Physiological Signals in HCI*, Honolulu, HI, USA. Retrieved from <https://arxiv.org/html/2405.13878v1>.

³⁶D3.1, p. 34.

³⁷Gallardo, Andrea, et al. "Speculative Privacy Concerns about AR Glasses Data Collection." *Proceedings on Privacy Enhancing Technologies*, 2023, pp. 416–435, <https://doi.org/10.56553/popets-2023-0117>.

³⁸See Hine, E., et al. (2024). Safety and privacy in immersive extended reality: An analysis and policy recommendations. *Digital Society*, 3(2), 1-40. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s44206-024-00114-1>.

³⁹D2.1, p. 19-22.

delves into the key aspect of consent-based processing, both for static data collected while registering new users and real-time collection of personal biometric data during the use of XR technologies.

- (a) **XR industry bodies:** The concerns regarding data protection requires entities offering products or services within the XR market to design their products in a human-centric manner. This involves undertaking value-sensitive design, incorporating ethical values such as privacy, dignity, transparency, and accountability, in the design of their products and/or services. Product and service providers in the XR market should implement measures in line with existing laws within the EU. This includes complying with the GDPR's provisions on processing data (including, but not limited to, consent), ensuring data security, and adhering to principles of the GDPR such as data minimisation, data protection by design, right to erasure, and conducting data protection impact assessments when a high risk to the rights and freedoms of data subjects is likely to happen. The amount of data collected by XR hardware and software providers will be limited if the requirements set by the GDPR are not effectively implemented from the legal and technical side. For example, the processing of bystander data by users of XR devices may require companies to decide between taking additional measures to collect such data lawfully, or, if not possible, not collecting it at all – both of which may be burdensome. In addition to GDPR compliance, industry leaders should collaborate to establish voluntary certification standards for XR devices, ensuring that privacy and security features are standardised across the market. Certification should offer clear benchmarks for data protection, giving consumers confidence in the technology they adopt.
- (b) **Policymakers and regulators:** As highlighted in this section, XR technologies raise several pressing concerns in terms of data protection, which sets limits and conditions to the production and deployment of applications. The relevant regulatory framework established by the EU is the GDPR. The GDPR is implemented by the European Data Protection Supervisor (EDPS) at the EU level and through national data protection authorities at the national level. Policymakers, both at the EU and at the member state level, play an important role in recognising the risks posed by XR technologies to data protection. The GDPR sets out obligations involving the need to take informed consent, requiring data processing to adhere to principles such as data minimisation, transparency and accountability, recognises rights for data subjects, and sets out obligations for companies and other entities in the XR ecosystem, when recognised as data controllers and processors (as described in D3.2). Regulators should consider the challenges and limitations for the development of XR technologies in the EU when implementing or even proposing future reforms to the GDPR, to meet the rights of data subjects, but not in a way that hinders the development of such technologies by EU-based companies.
- (c) **Research and academic organisations:** Researchers and academic organisations play a pivotal role in identifying and mitigating privacy risks posed by XR technologies. Independent audits of XR devices are essential to evaluate privacy vulnerabilities, particularly regarding the collection and processing of sensitive biometric data such as eye movements, facial expressions, and body scans. These audits can highlight gaps in current data protection measures and provide empirical evidence to support the development of robust privacy safeguards. Additionally, researchers must develop metrics to assess the impact of XR technologies on privacy, particularly for vulnerable groups, and evaluate the effectiveness of existing regulatory frameworks such as the GDPR. By conducting comprehensive studies, researchers can provide evidence-based insights to inform policymaking and industry practices, ensuring that privacy risks are addressed proactively. Furthermore, academic

organisations should contribute to public awareness by disseminating research findings and educating stakeholders, including developers, regulators, and users, on the evolving privacy challenges in XR ecosystems.

- (d) **Individuals (Users and General Public):** The role of individuals, including both users and the public, is central to ensuring accountability and promoting responsible XR usage. Enhancing digital literacy is critical for empowering users to understand how XR technologies collect, process, and utilise their data, particularly sensitive biometric information. Awareness programs should educate users about their data protection rights under frameworks such as the GDPR and provide practical guidance on identifying and mitigating privacy risks. For instance, users should be encouraged to review and customise privacy settings, carefully evaluate consent options, and recognise the implications of data processing in XR environments. Moreover, individuals can contribute to greater accountability by supporting consumer advocacy initiatives that promote transparency and ethical practices in XR development. Through informed decision-making and active engagement, individuals can play an active role in fostering a safer and more privacy-conscious XR ecosystem.

3.2. Agency, identity, and psychological health

Another prominent thematic issue that seems to overlap in the ethical and policy reviews is the risk posed by XR technologies on the identity, agency, and psychological health of users. The use of XR technologies has been linked with psychological impacts on the user. This section discusses the negative impacts of XR technologies identified in the previous WP reports and notes their impact on stakeholders. These impacts play out in three broad categories – impact on autonomy and agency, impact on identity, and impact on the user’s psychological health. D2.1 highlights the risks posed to autonomy and agency in terms of non-manipulation of individuals and freedom of choice.⁴⁰ The same issue was reflected in the policy review by D3.1, which points out the risk of emotional manipulation when XR technologies allows advertisers to process vast amounts of personal data for marketing purposes.⁴¹ The use of XR technologies in the marketing sector can also infringe the user’s consumer rights, as the real-world product or experience may feel much different than what is offered to the user via ‘experience marketing’ advertisements.⁴² Similarly, the validity of consent in educational and workplace settings raises concerns about user autonomy and agency. Power imbalances between employers and employees, or students and institutions, may limit the ability of users to freely make decisions regarding their engagement with XR technologies.⁴³

Similarly, D2.1 touches on the potential impacts of XR technologies on the user’s psychological health. This includes impacts to their identity and to their sense of self. Moreover, the report discusses the risks to a person’s own identity when engaging with XR technologies, highlighting the risks of depersonalisation and loss of agency and autonomy felt particularly by vulnerable user groups when re-entering the physical world.⁴⁴ This sense of depersonalisation and loss of identity is also highlighted in the use of XR technologies in the

⁴⁰D2.1, p. 21-22.

⁴¹D3.1, p. 24.

⁴²D3.1, p. 24.

⁴³D3.1, pp. 18 and 30.

⁴⁴D2.1, p. 16.

media and entertainment sector by D3.1.⁴⁵ XR technologies also opens new avenues of potentially experiencing a violation of one's identity and self. For example, D2.1 highlights the need to protect the virtual identity of XR technologies users to protect them from identity theft or hacking.⁴⁶ Similarly, D3.1 highlights that the use of XR technologies in the media and entertainment sector could risk harassment of users by other individuals including virtual sexual assaults of adults and children.⁴⁷ This concern is also reflected in the ethical review of the impact of XR technologies on society, economy and the environment. D2.1 highlights the potential of XR technologies in facilitating cybercrimes such as fraud, identity theft, sexual harassment or hacking.⁴⁸ D3.1 further notes that children are particularly vulnerable in the metaverse, and emphasises the need for protection against grooming, child sexual abuse, gambling addiction or doxing.^{49,50}

Additionally, D2.2 notes that XR technologies introduce significant epistemic uncertainties, as virtual environments can manipulate sensory experiences, making it difficult to distinguish between reality and simulation. This uncertainty extends to issues of avatar identity and trust, where it is challenging to verify the authenticity of virtual identities and interactions, potentially exacerbated by AI.⁵¹

Lastly, the use of XR technologies has been linked with impacts to the psychological health of the users. D2.1 notes that the psychological impact of XR manifests as depression, trauma, and aggressive behaviour for users.⁵² These harms may be exacerbated by the potentially addictive potential of XR technologies due to its immersive capabilities, and D3.1 notes that due to the levels of immersion and interactions with other users, VR applications in the media and entertainment sector can be highly addictive, resulting in greater depersonalisation and detachment from one's identity and agency.⁵³ Addiction to XR technologies also presents a larger issue in terms of its impact on society and relationships. As users get invested in their virtual identities, they may continue to dissociate from physical world by turning away from human interactions and relationships and instead resorting to getting gratification from within digital (virtual) environments.^{54,55}

3.2.1. Impact on stakeholders

The issues relating to freedom of thought, mental integrity, and agency, highlighted by D2.1 and D3.1, impact the users of XR technologies. The use of XR technologies raises issues in terms of autonomy and agency for users. Like the data protection impacts, the use of XR technologies for education, training, employment, or

⁴⁵D3.1, p. 15.

⁴⁶D2.1, p. 17.

⁴⁷D3.1, pp. 15-16.

⁴⁸D2.1, p. 17.

⁴⁹D3.1, pp. 38-39.

⁵⁰ Defined by the Dutch DPA as "the collection or disclosure of someone else's personal data for the purpose of scaring or harassing that person. For example, by posting a home address or telephone number online. Doxing is punishable." Autoriteit Persoonsgegevens. "Doxing." Accessed January 27, 2025. [Doxing en persoonsgegevens](#)

⁵¹D2.2 p. 36.

⁵²D2.1, p. 17.

⁵³D3.1, p. 15.

⁵⁴D3.1, pp. 39-40.

⁵⁵It is important to note that virtual reality is not "unreal" but rather a form of reality itself, and thus, a distinction between digital and physical realities may be more appropriate for understanding these dynamics.

skill development raises questions on the validity of the user's consent, given the power imbalance in these relationships. For example, the use of XR technologies in primary and secondary educational institutions requires the processing of personal data of children, which requires the consent of the children's parents or legal guardians. In addition to such uses having an impact on the data protection rights of children, the fiduciary role of students of all ages in an educational institution also creates a power imbalance for the students, impacting their autonomy and agency in the process.⁵⁶ For the use of XR in mandatory activities such as examinations, consent would no longer be viable and another legal basis must be chosen (e.g. public interest), with the effect that data collected and processed by the XR device must be limited by the purpose associated with that legal basis.

Users from vulnerable populations, including neurodivergent individuals and children, are particularly at risk in XR environments due to their limited capacity to recognise or mitigate these impacts.⁵⁷ For instance, prolonged use of XR by children can exacerbate psychological strain, resulting in dependency behaviours or detachment from reality. Similarly, neurodivergent users may experience heightened stress or overstimulation, necessitating safeguards such as tailored usage limits and adaptive settings to ensure safe interaction.⁵⁸

Further, D3.1 notes that XR technologies present the risk of manipulation as larger datasets may effectively draw out intimate preferences of users, including when used by advertisers for targeted marketing and deploying manipulative communication through deepfakes to disrupt democratic processes.⁵⁹ Furthermore, XR technologies have been linked with addictive use due to the immersive nature of this medium, and attendant issues of depersonalisation, derealisation, and depression.⁶⁰ This is particularly relevant in entertainment and gaming contexts.⁶¹ These impacts are compounded by the lack of tools to help users recognise and manage early signs of dependency. Individuals can face negative impacts due to actions of other users as well, including cyberbullying, virtual sexual assaults, fraud, identity theft or hacking. The impact of these harms by other users is exacerbated by the immersive nature of XR technologies. Additionally, risks

⁵⁶ Recital 43 of the GDPR notes that consent should not be a valid ground for processing personal data when there is a clear imbalance between the controller and the data subject.

⁵⁷ Jones, D., Ghasemi, S., Gračanin, D., & Azab, M. (2023). Privacy, safety, and security in extended reality: User experience challenges for neurodiverse users. In A. Moallem (Ed.), *HCI for Cybersecurity, Privacy and Trust. Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, 14045. Springer, Cham, 511–528. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-35822-7_33.

⁵⁸ See Lukava et al., suggesting that enabling the customisation of sensory settings, such as controlling the appearance or intensity of visual and auditory stimuli, could improve their experience. In Lukava, T., Morgado Ramirez, D. Z., & Barbareschi, G. (2022). Two sides of the same coin: Accessibility practices and neurodivergent users' experience of extended reality. *Journal of Enabling Technologies*, 16(2), 75–90. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JET-03-2022-0025>

⁵⁹ D3.1, p. 22, 40.

⁶⁰ Snijer, D., et al. (2020). *Responsible VR: Protect consumers in virtual reality*. Rathenau Instituut. Retrieved from <https://www.rathenau.nl/sites/default/files/2020-03/Responsible%20VR.pdf>; Madary, M., & Metzinger, T. (2016). Real virtuality: A code of ethical conduct. Recommendations for good scientific practice and the consumers of VR-technology. *Frontiers in Robotics and AI*, 3. <https://doi.org/10.3389/frobt.2016.00003>.

⁶¹ Kourtesis, P. (2024). A comprehensive review of multimodal XR applications, risks, and ethical challenges in the metaverse. *Multimodal Technologies and Interaction*, 8(11). <https://doi.org/10.3390/mti8110098>.

to personal identity are heightened in XR spaces, where unauthorised augmentation of virtual appearances ('reskinning rights') and virtual harassment can undermine users' sense of agency and autonomy.⁶² These risks necessitate mechanisms to safeguard digital identities and prevent exploitation in shared virtual environments.

3.2.2. Role of stakeholders in addressing challenges

- (a) **Policymakers:** The risks posed by XR technologies requires policymakers to take regulatory action to mitigate harms. The Charter of the Fundamental Rights of the European Union guarantee the right to mental integrity and the right to freedom of thought.⁶³ Unlike data protection issues, obligations relating to psychological health mental integrity are disparate and take the shape of prohibiting deceptive designs or dark patterns, in addition to new measures to ensure a safer internet for children.⁶⁴ Risks that can be exacerbated by the immersive nature of XR technologies, such as addiction, depersonalisation and derealisation, do not appear to be directly addressed in the European legal framework. In the policy domain, such governance frameworks play a vital role in addressing these novel concerns and developing frameworks that protect the mental integrity and agency of impacted users. To address these challenges, policymakers must develop ethical standards and legal safeguards to protect users from emotional manipulation, addiction, and identity violations. These measures should also address novel issues such as unauthorised augmentation of digital appearances ("reskinning rights") and virtual harassment, which raise significant concerns about user autonomy and psychological well-being. Regulatory oversight must extend to emerging risks, ensuring that XR technologies align with established protections for individual rights. The EU and its institutions also play an important role in furthering necessary research into these areas by funding projects examining the impacts of XR technologies.

Lastly, XR stakeholders need to ensure creating accountability models that enable recourse and redress for social and economic harms. Policymakers play a key role in ensuring that these are representative of all stakeholders, allowing participants, creators, and providers to benefit irrespective of location. Moreover, while transgressions and cybercrimes may be occurring within XR, the physical world must indicate how the international and global community should address these digital/virtual services to ensure/create safe digital spaces benefiting all.

⁶² Malik, T. (2024, May 9). *Physical solutions in virtual spaces: Challenges to content moderation in XR*. Tech Policy Press. Retrieved December 20, 2024, from <https://www.techpolicy.press/physical-solutions-in-virtual-spaces-challenges-to-content-moderation-in-xr/>

⁶³ Article 3, 10, Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union, 2000.

⁶⁴ A novel project in this regard that seeks to protect child rights in this sector is the EU's Better Internet for Kids (BIK+) project. This project focuses on ensuring a better digital experience for children, by inter alia developing age-appropriate design and standardising age verification methods. See European Commission. (2022). Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions – A digital decade for children and youth: The new European strategy for a better internet for kids (BIK+) (COM/2022/212). Retrieved from <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=COM:2022:212:FIN>

- (b) **Members of Research Ethics Committees (RECs):** Research ethics committees (RECs) play a crucial role in addressing the ethical challenges posed by XR technologies. They must develop policies and evaluate research proposals to ensure ethical standards are upheld, focusing on risks such as addiction, emotional manipulation, and identity violations, particularly for vulnerable populations like children and neurodivergent individuals. To ensure informed consent processes are robust, RECs must evaluate scenarios where XR technologies may exploit power imbalances or obscure the extent of data collection. Safeguards for participants' mental integrity and identity are critical, with particular attention to reducing psychological strain and preventing unauthorised manipulation of virtual appearances. RECs must also collaborate with researchers, developers, and policymakers to address emerging risks and develop actionable guidelines that reflect advancements in XR technologies. Ongoing training is essential to equip REC members with the expertise needed to navigate the complex and evolving ethical dimensions of XR technologies.
- (c) **XR industry bodies:** The harms posed by XR technologies in terms of mental integrity and agency must be considered when designing and using XR-based products and services. XR products and services must be designed and deployed in a human-centric and ethical manner, considering risks for users. Similarly, virtual safety bubbles, as deployed by Meta in Horizon Worlds and Horizon Venues, are examples of design choices aimed at tackling virtual sexual harassment.⁶⁵ Developers of XR services may incorporate similar design choices to address the other risks listed above. In addition to these measures, XR providers should prioritise privacy-by-design approaches that include features like real-time anonymisation, secure local processing, and robust safeguards for biometric data. These measures are particularly important for addressing risks such as emotional profiling and behavioural manipulation, which can undermine user autonomy and agency. Establishing voluntary certification standards for XR devices and services would provide industry-wide benchmarks for privacy, security, and ethical design. These standards would foster consumer trust while encouraging innovation within a framework of accountability. Clear and transparent communication with users is essential to help them understand data processing practices and the safeguards in place. For example, providing relatable scenarios about how their biometric data is collected, processed, and protected can empower users to make informed decisions. Lastly, carrying out a fundamental rights impact assessment (similarly to the obligation of the AI Act)⁶⁶ would require XR service providers to consider the risks posed to their users' mental integrity, and take mitigation steps to be implemented for the identified risks.
- (d) **Research:** As XR is a relatively nascent technology, there is an urgent need for deeper research into its impact and risks posed to individual users and the public. Long term and sufficiently powered research on diverse populations is particularly necessary for known and novel harms, such as harms to mental integrity and their consequences. Developing metrics to evaluate safeguards and ethical practices in XR technologies is essential, providing measurable indicators of psychological impacts, user autonomy, and mitigation success. Research should prioritise vulnerable populations, such as children, neurodivergent individuals, and economically disadvantaged groups, examining risks like

⁶⁵ Tabahrity, S. (2022, February 5). Meta is putting a stop to virtual groping in its metaverse by creating 4-foot safety bubbles around avatars. *Business Insider*. Retrieved from <https://www.businessinsider.com/meta-metaverse-virtual-groping-personal-boundary-safety-bubble-horizons-venues-2022-2>.

⁶⁶ Art. 27 AI Act.

emotional manipulation, psychological strain, and accessibility barriers. Collaboration between researchers, policymakers, and industry stakeholders is crucial to translating findings into actionable guidelines, ethical standards, and protective solutions. The domain of research also includes publicising and disseminating relevant information regarding the impact of XR technologies on psychological health. Public-facing research summaries, educational campaigns, and accessible tools should be developed to raise awareness among users and stakeholders about the risks and potential mitigations associated with XR technologies.

3.3. Physical health and well-being

The ethical and policy reviews of XR technologies and its applications highlight the impact on the physical health of users. These impacts include both the direct harms caused by the equipment and the manifestations of psychological impacts in physical health. In terms of direct harms, D3.1 notes that XR users may get physically injured in the physical world as their senses may be impaired and immersed in the virtual environment.⁶⁷ Similarly, D3.1 cites a case in Germany where a user, playing a game on his VR headset suffered cervical spinal vertebra injury due to the rapid body movements required by the game, as one of many examples in this regard.⁶⁸

XR technologies, its equipment and its functionality may also indirectly manifest physical effects of its mental impact. For example, D2.1 highlights the physical harms of immersive technology that include nausea, vomiting, disorientation or palpitations, which may also manifest because of users re-entering the real-world environment.⁶⁹ D3.1 notes that a common side effect of XR technologies is simulator sickness, i.e., a phenomenon akin to motion sickness experienced by users of XR technologies that might trigger eye fatigue, disorientation and nausea.⁷⁰ Symptoms of simulator sickness have been noted in the medical and psychological field.⁷¹ It further notes that although there are several guidelines in place for addressing simulator sickness, the extent to which these guidelines are implemented is unclear.⁷² Lastly, D3.1 notes that in the context of military operations, the use of AR headsets has reportedly caused physical impairment of soldiers in the US Army.⁷³

3.3.1. Impact on stakeholders

The issues relating to physical health concerns raised by XR technologies, highlighted by WP 2 and 3, impact the following stakeholders:

⁶⁷ D3.1, p. 15.

⁶⁸ Ibid.

⁶⁹ D2.1, pp. 16-17.

⁷⁰ Chang, E., Kim, H. T., & Yoo, B. (2020). Virtual reality sickness: A review of causes and measurements. *International Journal of Human-Computer Interaction*, 36(17), 1-17. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10447318.2020.1778351>

⁷¹ D3.1, p. 22.

⁷² Ibid.

⁷³ D3.1, p. 27.

- (a) **Users of XR technologies:** XR users can undergo cybersickness, with symptoms of disorientation, nausea, loss of spatial awareness, eye soreness, reduced depth perception and hand-eye coordination, and loss of balance.⁷⁴ These effects can be exacerbated during prolonged use, potentially leading to “eye strain, musculoskeletal issues, and sedentary lifestyles”.⁷⁵ D3.1 further notes the risks to physical injury through the use of XR technologies, in the context of players suffering spinal injuries due to the rapid or repetitive movements required in VR application (specifically games). Emerging concerns include injuries resulting from users’ impaired awareness of their physical surroundings, emphasising the importance of built-in safety features like boundary warnings and spatial awareness tools.

The use of XR technologies in public or shared environments raises significant safety concerns, particularly in location-based experiences such as outdoor games or geo-fenced activities. XR use in these settings can inadvertently cause harm or nuisance to bystanders, leading to risks such as collisions or injuries. A notable example is the case in the United States where drivers of semi-autonomous vehicles wearing Apple Vision Pro headsets raised safety concerns about traffic accidents.⁷⁶ Although these headsets provide a mixed reality (MR) experience, they are not designed for use while operating a vehicle.⁷⁷ In shared public spaces, bystanders may also face risks from XR users who experience reduced spatial awareness, underscoring the need for clear guidelines and safety protocols. Establishing these measures is essential to ensuring public safety and minimising the potential for accidents or disturbances caused by XR technologies.

3.3.2. Role of stakeholders in addressing challenges

- (a) **Policy makers:** Policymakers have a critical role in mitigating the physical harms associated with XR technologies. Regulatory guidance should include advisories and restrictions for scenarios where partitioned attention poses significant risks, such as driving or operating heavy machinery. Public awareness campaigns are essential to educate users on physical risks like cybersickness, eye strain, and disorientation, while promoting safe practices such as taking breaks and adjusting device settings. Harmonised health standards, developed in collaboration with industry bodies, should address issues such as motion sickness, vision strain, and musculoskeletal health, providing clear

⁷⁴ Department for Business and Trade, Office for Product Safety and Standards, & Department for Business, Energy & Industrial Strategy. (2020, September). *The safety of domestic virtual reality systems: A literature review* (BEIS Research Paper Number 2020/038). Retrieved from <https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/5f763502d3bf7f7c2bcf9eb9/safety-domestic-vr-systems.pdf>

⁷⁵ Kourtesis, Panagiotis. ‘A Comprehensive Review of Multimodal XR Applications, Risks, and Ethical Challenges in the Metaverse.’ *Multimodal Technologies and Interaction* 8.11 (2024): 1-46. 20 December 2024. <https://doi.org/10.3390/mti8110098>.

⁷⁶ DigWatch. (2024, February 7). *Safety warning issued for drivers wearing Apple Vision Pro headsets*. Retrieved from <https://dig.watch/updates/safety-warning-issued-for-drivers-wearing-apple-vision-pro-headsets>

⁷⁷ Sky News. (2024, February 6). *Concerns raised over Tesla drivers using VR headsets*. Retrieved from <https://news.sky.com/story/concerns-raised-over-tesla-drivers-using-vr-headsets-13065155>

guidance for developers and manufacturers to ensure user safety.

- (b) **Researchers and programmers:** Researchers and programmers are integral to mitigating the potential harms and risks caused by XR technologies. Further research is needed to assess the long-term impacts of XR user such as vision strain, musculoskeletal health, and motion-related issues, through longitudinal studies. These studies are vital for developing evidence-based guidelines and improving device safety. Innovative design solutions, including frame rate optimisation, enhanced motion tracking, and adaptive visual settings, should be explored and integrated into XR functionality to reduce motion sickness and discomfort.^{78,79} Developing standardised metrics for evaluating the physical health impacts of XR technologies is essential. These metrics can help identify areas requiring improvement and assess the effectiveness of mitigation strategies. Collaboration with policymakers, industry leaders, and health professionals is crucial to ensure research findings inform actionable safety standards. Science journalists also play a key role in raising public awareness by disseminating and publicising innovations in XR design that can help mitigate these attendant issues and simultaneously increase user awareness regarding the physical health risks, empowering users with knowledge to adopt safer practices.
- (c) **XR industry bodies:** XR industry bodies, including hardware and software providers, play a vital role in mitigating physical and psychological risks through the design and development of XR technologies. This requires fostering interoperability across internal teams and incorporating diverse perspectives throughout the product lifecycle—from ideation and production to deployment. A human-centric approach must guide development, ensuring that potential mental and physical harms are carefully considered and addressed as core elements of product design.

Industry bodies should incorporate built-in safety features into XR devices, such as spatial awareness tools, boundary warnings, and pass-through camera views, to minimise risks of injury or disorientation. For example, the boundary settings in Meta Quest 3 allow users to draw a boundary based on the free space around them.⁸⁰ To address motion sickness, adaptive visual and motion settings, including frame rate optimisation and user-adjustable comfort levels, should be prioritised. Hygiene concerns, particularly for shared or rental devices, must also be addressed through sanitisation protocols and materials that minimise skin irritation and cross-contamination.

⁷⁸ Shi, R., et al. (2021). Virtual reality sickness mitigation methods: A comparative study in a racing game. *Proceedings of the ACM on Computer Graphics and Interactive Techniques*, 4(1). <https://doi.org/10.1145/3451255>

⁷⁹ For example, see Worker exposure to virtual and augmented Reality and metaverse technologies: How much do we know?. European Agency for Safety and Health at Work. (2024). *Worker exposure to virtual and augmented reality and metaverse technologies: How much do we know? Discussion papers*. Retrieved December 20, 2024, from <https://osha.europa.eu/en/publications/worker-exposure-virtual-and-augmented-reality-and-metaverse-technologies-how-much-do-we-know>

⁸⁰ 'Suggested boundary and assisted space setup on Meta Quest 3' Ge Meta. (n.d.). *Suggested boundary and assisted space setup on Meta Quest 3*. Retrieved from <https://www.meta.com/en-gb/help/quest/articles/getting-started/getting-started-with-quest-3/suggested-boundary-assisted-space-setup/>.

Comprehensive testing of XR hardware and software for physical safety is essential prior to market release. This includes evaluating devices for musculoskeletal strain, vision health, and prolonged usage impacts, with compliance to established safety standards verified.

Organisations in the XR sector have called for stronger standards and industry-wide collaboration to establish benchmarks for physical health and safety.⁸¹ This could include contributing to the development of the Code of Conduct through stakeholder-led discussions facilitated by the XR4Human project. Industry bodies should actively promote user education by providing clear guidance on safe usage practices, such as session limits and techniques to reduce physical harm. This information should be delivered through user manuals, on-device notifications, and interactive tutorials embedded within XR applications.

- (d) **Users of XR technologies:** Individual users play a critical role in protecting their physical well-being when engaging with XR technologies. By adopting safe practices—such as limiting session durations, taking regular breaks, and adjusting settings like brightness and motion sensitivity—users can mitigate risks like cybersickness, eye strain, and musculoskeletal issues. Built-in safety features, including boundary warnings and pass-through camera modes, help prevent injury and enhance spatial awareness.

Users also have agency in staying informed about XR health impacts through product manuals, community forums, and industry guidance. By providing feedback to developers and advocating for ergonomic and accessible designs, users can influence safer XR development. Through responsible use and active engagement, individual users contribute to fostering safer and more inclusive XR environments.

3.4. Discrimination, disparity, and accessibility concerns

The use of XR technologies has been noted as a potential cause for discrimination by the ethical and policy reviews within D2.1 and D3.1, respectively. The modes of discrimination are diverse and range from economic disparity to accessibility concerns. From a human rights perspective, the D2.1 flags concerns regarding discrimination against vulnerable and marginalised people, including users with mental illnesses and child users.⁸² D3.1 notes the potential of XR technologies overwhelming users with mental disabilities through the sudden change in environmental and specific sensory experiences, due to XR's immersive nature.⁸³ Furthermore, XR technologies may not be financially accessible for people in all strata of society and might exacerbate the harms caused by the lack of privilege for economically disadvantaged individuals. In this regard, D2.1 highlights that rising adoption of XR technologies raises concerns of social inclusivity and user exclusion, potentially deepening existing digital divides and limiting access to education, training, and

⁸¹ For example, see 'Immersive Technology Standards for accessibility, inclusion, ethics, and safety' (2020) CyberXR Coalition. https://cyberxr.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/05/Immersive_Technology_Standards.pdf.

⁸² D2.1, p. 17.

⁸³ D3.1, p. 30.

economic opportunities.⁸⁴ Similarly, D3.1 notes that the use of XR technologies in the workplace, for instance, may require additional training and access to XR technologies by employees, and might be an entry barrier for economically disadvantaged job seekers.⁸⁵ Lastly, D3.1 notes the need for upskilling users for XR technologies through education, training, and professional development to prevent skill gap, given the rapid pace of innovation and the relative novelty of XR technologies.⁸⁶ A key aspect of the challenges presented by XR technologies regarding discrimination involves the lack of access and representation for people with varying levels, types and degrees of disabilities.⁸⁷ D3.1 notes that individuals with certain disabilities that include those based on vision, hearing, mobility or cognition may be disadvantaged in a workplace that relies on XR technologies, if the XR technologies has not fully been adapted to factor in such circumstances.⁸⁸ While D3.1 cites studies that particularly refer to accessibility concerns for persons with disabilities in the workplace, these individuals may face accessibility issues with under-adapted XR technologies across sectors, including education, media and entertainment uses of XR technologies.⁸⁹

3.4.1. Impact on stakeholders

The issues relating to concerns of discrimination, disparity and accessibility raised by XR technologies, highlighted by D2.1 and D3.1, impact the following stakeholders:

- (a) **Users of XR technologies:** In terms of discrimination and disparity, the lack of digital literacy and the lack of familiarity with XR devices for economic reasons can exacerbate discrimination. This is relevant in instances where knowledge and familiarity with XR devices are required for the purposes of education, training, or employment, and where knowledge of and access to XR technologies are increasingly becoming prerequisites. High costs of XR hardware and software exclude economically disadvantaged individuals and smaller organisations, preventing them from accessing the benefits of these technologies. This exclusion widens existing socioeconomic disparities, particularly in sectors that increasingly rely on XR for upskilling and participation in the digital economy. XR devices that are not designed to be universally accessible can cause discriminatory effects for people with disabilities, including people suffering from visual, mobility, cognition, or hearing impairments. Beyond physical disabilities, neurodivergent users, such as those with autism spectrum disorder or ADHD, may face additional challenges in XR environments. Features such as overstimulating visuals or rapid transitions can create cognitive overload, limiting usability and increasing exclusion.
- (b) **General public:** Issues regarding lack of accessibility and lack of economic status may exclude various strata of society from being able to access XR products or services. As mentioned above, a lack of access or familiarity with XR services or products, when deployed in educational institutions or workplaces, may negatively impact the public and may pose as a barrier to entry for education,

⁸⁴ D2.1, p. 17.

⁸⁵ D3.1, p. 18.

⁸⁶ Ibid.

⁸⁷ D2.1, p. 17.

⁸⁸ D3.1, p. 18.

⁸⁹ IEEE. (2022). Extended reality (XR) ethics and diversity, inclusion, and accessibility. *Industry Connections Report*. https://standards.ieee.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/04/Ethics_Diversity_Inclusion_Accessibility.pdf.

upskilling or employment opportunities. Uneven infrastructure development further exacerbates these challenges, particularly in rural or underserved regions where access to XR hardware, reliable internet connectivity, or geospatial data is limited. This geographic inequality creates a digital divide, preventing entire communities from benefitting from XR technologies in areas such as education, healthcare, and workforce training. In addition to accessibility concerns, the lack of diverse representation in XR content risks alienating certain groups within the public. For instance, underrepresentation of minority cultures or marginalised communities in XR experiences can reinforce stereotypes and limit the inclusivity of these platforms. Creating XR content that reflects diverse identities and perspectives is essential for fostering a sense of belonging and equal participation.

3.4.2. Role of stakeholders in addressing challenges

- (a) **Policy makers:** Policymakers play a critical role in addressing discrimination and accessibility challenges in XR technologies. Soft law, including the development of industry standards, can help mitigate these issues by promoting universal accessibility. Establishing mandatory accessibility standards for XR devices and applications—like existing web accessibility guidelines—can ensure XR technologies accommodate users with disabilities. This includes integrating features such as voice navigation, adaptive controllers, and text-to-speech functionality.⁹⁰ By implementing these measures, policymakers can ensure XR technologies are inclusive and usable for individuals of all physical and cognitive abilities. D2.1 highlights the importance of guidelines that address not only accessibility but also economic disparities and the potential for exploitation, further reinforcing the need for equitable XR adoption.⁹¹
- (b) **Research and academic organisations:** Research into the design of XR technologies and the vulnerabilities of design principles for people with accessibility issues is required to flag potential risks of discriminatory design. Researchers and programmers play an important role in guiding and framing the design principles underpinning XR services and products. For example, communities such as 'XR Access,' a research consortium based in Cornell University, seek to build, and share knowledge to make XR accessible and inclusive for all users.⁹² Researchers should develop standardised metrics to evaluate the accessibility and inclusivity of XR technologies. These metrics can help assess whether XR products effectively address the needs of diverse user groups and provide benchmarks for continuous improvement. Moreover, academic institutions should assess representation within XR content, identifying gaps in how different cultures, identities, and marginalised communities are portrayed. These studies can guide developers to create more representative and inclusive virtual experiences.

⁹⁰ See The Web Accessibility Directive ([Directive \(EU\) 2016/2102](https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:32016L2102&from=EN)) <<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:32016L2102&from=EN>>

⁹¹ D2.1, p. 24.

⁹² 'XR Access. (n.d.). *About XR Access: Virtual, augmented, and mixed reality for people with disabilities*. Retrieved from <https://xraccess.org/about/>; for examples of research see Collins, J. (2023). "The guide has your back": Exploring how sighted guides can enhance accessibility in social virtual reality for blind and low vision people. *ASSETS '23: Proceedings of the 25th International ACM SIGACCESS Conference on Computers and Accessibility*, Article 38. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3597638.3608386>

- (c) **Science journalists:** they play a key role in enhancing digital literacy and spreading awareness for users regarding their rights and legitimate interests for users to make informed decisions prior to using XR products and/or services. Further, journalists can also help highlight the unique challenges faced by differently users, which raises awareness for the need to ensure universal accessibility of XR technologies.
- (d) **XR industry bodies:** XR developers and service providers must prioritise inclusivity and accessibility throughout the design, development, and deployment of XR products and services. Input from researchers, journalists, and academic organisations can help identify design gaps that industry can address. Collaboration with these stakeholders ensures that ethics and policymaking are embedded into XR development, fostering more responsible innovation.

Industry bodies should integrate inclusive design principles across the product lifecycle, incorporating features such as voice navigation, haptic feedback, and text-to-speech tools to accommodate users with disabilities. Adaptive interfaces and controllers can further enhance usability for individuals with diverse physical, cognitive, or sensory needs.

To address economic disparities, XR developers can implement tiered pricing models, affordable hardware solutions, and open-source software initiatives. These strategies reduce costs and improve access to XR technologies, benefiting economically disadvantaged users and smaller organisations, particularly in education and workforce development.

XR service providers must also ensure that the content they create, or host, represents diverse cultures, identities, and experiences. Avoiding stereotypes and amplifying underrepresented voices is essential to fostering inclusive XR environments. Partnering with advocacy groups and researchers can help shape equitable content that reflects a wide range of perspectives.

Industry bodies are recognised as key stakeholders in the XR4Human project and play a vital role in addressing accessibility and discrimination. Their input will enhance the development and effectiveness of the Code of Conduct produced through this initiative.

3.5. The need for strengthening the XR market and reducing the barriers to entry

The XR market in the EU is currently at a nascent stage. However, it has been predicted to grow at an exponential rate in the years to come. WP 3.1 notes that the global XR market is projected to add 1.3 trillion euros to the global economy by 2030, with estimates of direct European employment in this sector ranging from 440,000 people to 860,000 people by 2025.⁹³ In this regard, WP 3 notes that there are concerns with the speed of adoption of XR technologies in the EU due to the fragmented nature of the ecosystem surrounding

⁹³ D3.1, pp. 34-35.

hardware, software and content creation.⁹⁴ Interoperability standards play a key role in addressing the fragmentation of this sector, highlighting the need for compatibility across different devices and systems in successful adoption and integration of XR technologies with other emerging technologies.⁹⁵ Human-centred interoperability includes both technical standardisation and the compatibility of these standards with ethical, legal and policy considerations that ensure the user's autonomy and their fundamental rights.⁹⁶ Ensuring human-centred interoperability through the Interoperability Guidance Document in the XR4Human project aims to reduce barriers to entry for start-ups and small businesses, and therefore makes this technology affordable and accessible to a larger portion of the population. Industry bodies highlight that regional standardisation could negatively impact small and medium European companies by increasing trade barriers, and instead, global and consensus-based interoperability standards can lead to economies of scale, reducing costs for consumers and fuelling healthy competition between XR providers.⁹⁷ Similarly, the World Economic Forum notes that making virtual environments interoperable would reduce the power of network effects for established companies, fostering competition and reducing barriers to entry for new entrants.⁹⁸

Further, a human-centred approach to interoperability which focuses on the user's experience may help build user engagement. XR technologies currently suffers from issues in providing a seamless experience for individuals. Interoperability standards that are designed to offer a seamless experience for users accessing platforms across different devices may enhance user experience and satisfaction.⁹⁹ Further, there are different components within the XR realm that can be targets of interoperability, i.e., specific interoperability needs vary for avatars, APIs, storage and gaming collectibles.¹⁰⁰ This layered understanding of interoperability as inclusive of user experience prompts human-centred standards. For example, the World Wide Web Consortium (W3C) has drafted user accessibility standards for the XR space, focusing on the needs and requirements of people with disabilities when using XR technologies.¹⁰¹

Lastly, interoperability in XR technologies might offer greater insights into the public use of XR technologies. D3.1 notes that standards act as force-multipliers for digital transformation and highlights the key role of standards in XR technologies.¹⁰² D3.1 cites the example of how XR technologies is used in the 'Digital Twins'

⁹⁴ Ibid, p. 37.

⁹⁵ Johannesson, P., & Karlsson, J. (2023). The early stages of extended reality: An analysis of the opportunities and challenges faced by early-stage businesses within the extended reality (XR) industry. *Thesis, Malmö University*. <https://mau.diva-portal.org/smash/get/diva2:1798250/FULLTEXT02.pdf>.

⁹⁶ D4.1, p. 16.

⁹⁷ XR Association 'XR Association response to European Commission's call for contributions on competition in virtual worlds and generative AI' (March 2024) p. 7 <https://xra.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/03/XRA-Response-to-EU-Consultation-on-Virtual-Worlds.pdf>

⁹⁸ Li, C. (2022). Who will govern the metaverse? *World Economic Forum*. <https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2022/05/metaverse-governance/>.

⁹⁹ XR4Human Project Proposal document, 'The Equitable, Inclusive, and Human-Centered XR Project (XR4HUMAN) HORIZON-CL4-2021-HUMAN-01-28

¹⁰⁰ LeewayHertz. (n.d.). Interoperability and the future of the metaverse. Retrieved from <https://www.leewayhertz.com/metaverse-interoperability/#What-is-Metaverse>.

¹⁰¹ World Wide Web Consortium. (2025, August 25). *XR accessibility user requirements*. Retrieved from <https://www.w3.org/TR/xaur/>.

¹⁰² D3.1, p. 31.

project, where the overground and underground infrastructure of a city can be captured in 3D imagery.¹⁰³ The Digital Twins project relies on open standards and open-source projects, evidencing the need for development of standards focusing on interoperability. In this regard, D3.1 notes that a broader adoption of the nascent standards being developed for XR technologies could support the interoperability required for using XR in such ‘systems-of-systems’ contexts like the Digital Twins project.¹⁰⁴ Advances in interoperability enables the European XR market in developing similar technology that can be deployed at scale due to the lowered barriers to entry in the market.

3.6. Interoperability and the need for standards

As discussed in the background to this report, XR technologies is an umbrella concept that includes VR, AR, and MR technology. A key element of XR technologies is the immersive experience felt by the user, with XR technologies ranges from creating a hyper-realistic portrayal of a virtual world for the user to introducing virtual objects into the physical world where virtual content intersects and merges with the physical environment starting to influence and affect many different aspects of our daily life. XR technologies encompasses a spectrum of diverse functionalities. WP 4 underscores the significance of spatial computing in delivering a deeply engaging experience for users of XR technologies, emphasising the multifaceted of the spatial web.¹⁰⁵ As highlighted by D4.1, interoperability requires integration of ethical and policy concerns from the foundational levels of design and development for ensuring a human-centric and ethical design of XR technologies. Accordingly, one of the major goals of the XR4Human project is to co-create an Interoperability Guidance Document with the European XR community and to disseminate the Interoperability Guidance Document through the European XR Forum.¹⁰⁶ Increased interoperability would allow greater access to XR services for European users, forging a competitive and sustainable ecosystem for the European XR industry. Lastly, interoperability plays a major role in enabling individuals to exercise control over their virtual identities across services. Virtual identities play a key role in interoperable XR by enabling accountability and the capability to traverse worlds with minimal friction. This needs a contextual framing of identities. Interoperable identity management by XR services can enable an individual to shape their digital identity in a nuanced manner.¹⁰⁷

The review of the existing state of technical interoperability by D4.1 raises significant interoperability-based challenges faced by XR technologies. Firstly, D4.1 notes that the current literature on XR technologies notes the lack of interoperability between systems, platforms, and data formats.¹⁰⁸ Secondly, most users of digital services today have a two-dimensional perspective of their current digital lives, including their use of 2D documents, the Internet, videos, and mobile applications. WP 4 notes that there is a lack of interoperability

¹⁰³ Ibid

¹⁰⁴ Ibid, p. 32

¹⁰⁵ D4.1, p. 5.

¹⁰⁶ XR4Human Project Proposal document, ‘The Equitable, Inclusive, and Human-Centered XR Project (XR4HUMAN) HORIZON-CL4-2021-HUMAN-01-28.

¹⁰⁷ Alkaeed, M., Qayyum, A., & Qadir, J. (2024). Privacy preservation in artificial intelligence and extended reality (AI-XR) metaverses: A survey. *Journal of Network and Computer Applications*, 231. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jnca.2024.1031668>

¹⁰⁸ D4.1, p. 7.

between the existing digital lives of users and the 3D spaces provided by XR technologies, significantly reducing the utility of XR spaces for users.¹⁰⁹ Users cannot change, and therefore are limited in their imagination to, existing 2D layouts.¹¹⁰ Lastly, D4.1 highlighted the difference between the development of XR technologies and the development of the Internet of Things (IoT) sector in terms of interoperability. While IoT has been developed keeping in mind standardisation and interoperability, D4.1 notes that XR has been developed differently focusing on isolated needs.¹¹¹

The proposed Interoperability Guidance Document aims to provide tailor-made standards, guidelines and frameworks that are more accessible and applicable for each stakeholder group, fostering greater interoperability. In this regard, D4.1 notes that the Interoperability Guidance Document must focus on three kinds of interoperability, i.e., technical interoperability, usage interoperability, and jurisdictional interoperability.¹¹²

3.6.1. Impact on stakeholders

The issues relating to concerns of interoperability impact the following stakeholders:

- (a) **Users of XR technologies:** Consumers benefit from a competitive XR market that fosters innovation and drives down costs. However, barriers to entry for small and medium European companies (SMEs) can lead to reduced consumer choice and higher prices as larger companies dominate the market. D4.1 notes the lack of interoperability between XR services and two-dimensional services, and its impact on users seeking to seamlessly integrate their existing digital life (in 2D spaces) with XR services. The lack of interoperability also impacts users as it reduces their choices. The inability to integrate different virtual experiences and identities can create a negative XR experience for users. This fragmentation reduces consumer options and creates inefficiencies, negatively affecting the overall XR experience. An inclusive and standardised XR ecosystem ensures greater access to diverse applications and services, particularly in sectors like education, healthcare, and entertainment. The inability to integrate different virtual experiences and identities limits users' ability to fully engage with XR technologies, creating frustrations and deterring widespread adoption.
- (b) **XR Industry Bodies:** Developers and industry bodies are directly impacted by the fragmentation of XR platforms and the lack of interoperability standards. These challenges increase development complexity, raise costs, and limit scalability, thereby reducing innovation. For SMEs the absence of regional standardisation exacerbates trade barriers and other entry challenges particularly for those working in niche XR markets.

3.6.2. Role of stakeholders in addressing challenges

¹⁰⁹ D4.1, p. 11-12.

¹¹⁰ Ibid.

¹¹¹ Ibid.

¹¹² D4.1, p. 18.

In addition to highlighting the key limitations of interoperability for XR technologies, D4.1 discusses the existing state of XR-related standards. Industry consortia comprising technology companies, private non-profit organisations and regional/global standardisation bodies have commenced developing standards and protocols for technical interoperability.¹¹³ These entities also correspond with three of the four personas of stakeholders discussed by D1.1, namely industry, non-profit organisations, and policymakers. Developing technical interoperability is key to increase consumer choice, foster greater supply helping greater adoption and scalability of the XR technologies sector, and to encourage research and innovation in the EU market, all of which ultimately benefit the public and the technology sector in the EU.¹¹⁴

D4.1 identifies the three layers of interoperability, i.e., the data and infrastructure layer, the stakeholder participation layer, and the experience management layer.¹¹⁵ Fostering technical interoperability through developing standards, protocols and coordinating adoption only at the data and infrastructure layer is not enough. At the stakeholder participation layer, in addition to technical interoperability, additional elements such as usage, and jurisdictional interoperability become relevant. Particularly, the usage and jurisdictional elements aim to ensure a multidisciplinary, diverse, and flexible approach when framing interoperability standards, from an ethical and policy perspective. In this regard, achieving human-centric interoperability involves an inclusive process that is accessible and seamlessly integrates with the ethical, policy and regulatory requirements of XR technologies.¹¹⁶ These principles guide D4.1 in co-creating the Interoperability Guidance Document along with the European XR community to help make such standards and guidelines available, accessible and easily implementable.

- (a) **Policy makers:** Development of standards that provide guidance on human-centric interoperability can mitigate the issues caused by lack of interoperability. As this paper notes above, focusing on human-centric interoperability, and not merely on technical interoperability, requires an interdisciplinary approach to designing XR services, where policymakers can play an important role. Further, European and global standardisation bodies serve as critical forums where policymakers can foster collaboration between developers, industry bodies, and researchers where such standards can be developed. Facilitating cross-industry partnerships and funding collaborative projects will accelerate the development and adoption of shared technical frameworks and interoperability benchmarks. Policymakers could also offer targeted support to SMEs, which are often disproportionately affected by interoperability challenges. Grants, tax incentives, and simplified procurement processes for public institutions can help smaller companies overcome barriers and compete effectively in the XR market. By encouraging innovation through funding programs for interoperable technologies they can further drive inclusivity and scalability.

- (b) **XR industry bodies:** These stakeholders, which include associations dedicated to industry, developers, and SMEs in the European and global XR market, play a key role in consensus-based standardisation. Industry bodies offer a forum for discussion, sharing best practices and agreeing on working towards recognised standards. The XR4Human project will design an Interoperability

¹¹³ D4.1, p. 13-14.

¹¹⁴ D4.1, p. 9.

¹¹⁵ D4.1, p. 10.

¹¹⁶ D4.1, p. 16.

Guidance Document, relying on the inputs by stakeholders, aiming to offer further clarity for entities operating in the European XR market.

- (c) **Researchers and programmers:** research plays a key role in developing human-centric interoperability, by designing standards, governance norms and building ethical values into the design of XR products and services. Close collaboration between end-users, programmers, researchers and industry bodies is essential to ensure that interoperability frameworks align with practical, real-world applications. By working together, they can develop standards that are not only technically robust but also user-friendly and reflective of ethical principles.

4. Reaffirming the objectives

The XR4Human project is a landmark initiative that addresses the multifaceted challenges posed by XR technologies through a collaborative, human-centred approach. This report synthesises insights from the project's deliverables, which examine XR technologies from diverse perspectives, including ethical, regulatory, technical, and societal dimensions. Collectively, these insights contribute to the development of a European Code of Conduct, Interoperability Guidelines, and educational tools and provides the foundations for the roadmap that is to be developed in WP3. Additionally, the project delivers an experience library featuring test cases, a rating system to assess XR solutions, and resources to support public awareness and responsible use, all aimed at fostering an equitable, inclusive, and sustainable XR ecosystem.

4.1. Synthesis of key insights

This report synthesises findings from the project's work packages (WPs) to identify and integrate critical areas of focus for XR technologies. Building on the ethical frameworks examined in D2.1, it highlights the importance of safeguarding sensitive biometric data and addressing the complexities of real-time data processing. Insights from D3.1 emphasise the risks of emotional manipulation, addiction, identity violations, and physical health concerns, such as motion sickness and long-term strain, advocating for safeguards to protect users' mental and physical well-being. Finally, D4.1's focus on technical and human-centric interoperability provides a foundation for promoting standards and reducing barriers to entry, ensuring a competitive and equitable XR market.

4.2. The role of stakeholders in addressing challenges

Addressing the complex challenges posed by XR technologies requires a collaborative effort from all stakeholders. Each group plays a distinct and complementary role in ensuring that XR technologies are developed and adopted in ways that uphold ethical principles, promote inclusivity, and address societal needs.

- **Policymakers:** Policymakers play a critical role in creating regulatory frameworks that translate the insights of this report into actionable policies. This could include establishing mandatory accessibility standards for XR devices and applications, developing funding mechanisms to support affordable solutions, and fostering the expansion of infrastructure to underserved regions. By providing a supportive regulatory and economic environment, policymakers enable equitable adoption of XR technologies across diverse populations.
- **XR industry Bodies:** Industry bodies, including developers, manufacturers, and associations, are pivotal in ensuring that XR technologies are designed and deployed ethically. Their role involves embedding affordability, accessibility, and inclusivity into all stages of product development, from ideation to deployment. By aligning their efforts with interoperability standards and addressing accessibility gaps, industry bodies contribute to creating XR technologies that serve a wide range of user needs.
- **Researchers and Academic Institutions:** The research community is essential in identifying and addressing the emerging challenges associated with XR technologies. Researchers contribute by developing evidence-based solutions, creating metrics to evaluate inclusivity and safety, and studying the long-term impacts of XR use. Through collaboration with industry and policymakers,

researchers ensure that their findings inform practical and effective approaches to the ethical development and use of XR technologies.

- End-Users and Science Journalists:** End-users and science journalists play crucial roles in shaping the responsible adoption of XR technologies. End-users provide practical insights into usability challenges and advocate for inclusive and ethical practices, ensuring that XR technologies align with societal values. Science journalists complement these efforts by raising awareness of XR risks and benefits, disseminating research findings, and highlighting the needs of underrepresented groups. Together, they drive accountability and promote a more equitable and human-centred approach to XR development.

Figure 2: Stakeholder Roles in Addressing XR technologies Challenges.

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